

WAYS OF ERROR CORRECTION IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

Over the course of the past few decades, a lot of attention has been paid to error correction and the significance of it in the classroom of foreign languages. Correcting students' mistakes is important, according to Corder (1967), in three different ways: First, they tell the teacher about the student's progress and what still needs to be learned. Second, they provide evidence of how a language is learned and the learning strategies employed by the student. Thirdly, because making mistakes is seen as a tool used by learners to learn, they are essential to the learning process. The purpose of this paper is to highlight fundamental Error Analysis background research. It also tries to educate EFL teachers and educators about the most common mistakes made by EFL students and encourages language practitioners to think about important questions about the significance of error correction in the process of learning a second language, such as: how much correction should be given, when the mistake should be made, and how to correct the student without making them less motivated.

Key words: *EFL, contrastive Analysis and error Analysis, error, error correction.*

INTRODUCTION

It is thought that learners receive feedback on how they use language through error correction. One of the most challenging aspects of language acquisition is assisting students in correcting the mistakes they make in writing and speaking. This is a fact that no educator can deny. As a result, error correction concerns should be taken into consideration by every language practitioner or educator: the distinction between an error and a mistake, the amount of correction that should be given, the phases at which the error should be corrected, and how the teacher can correct the student without demotivating them. Understanding the nature of learning a foreign or second language, i.e., how do we learn a second language, is one essential aspect of error correction. To learn a language, we must investigate the mental processes that take place in human minds. American linguist Krashen (1987) distinguished two phenomena in this regard when he made a clear distinction between: learning a second language in addition to learning a first language. In linguistics and psycholinguistics,

various schools emerged with the goal of analyzing students' errors and deciphering their sources. The structural behaviorist school and the transformational generative grammarians are two of those schools. In the field of learning second and foreign languages, contrastive analysis (CA) and error analysis (EA) have been regarded as the two primary pillars. "...there have been two major approaches to the study of learners' errors, namely Contrastive Analysis and Error Analysis," as stated by Keshavarz (1999, p. 11). "Error Analysis emerged on account of the shortcomings of Contrastive Analysis, which was the preferred way of describing learners' language in the 1950s and 1960s," he went on to say (p. 42). The comparison of the learners' native language and the target language is the process that is involved in CA. Errors that students would be most likely to commit were predicted based on the similarities and differences between the two languages (Kim, 2001). James (1998, cited in Kim, 2001) stated that, in contrast to CA, which tries to describe the differences and similarities between L1 and L2, EA tries to independently and objectively describe learners' interlanguage, or learners' version of the target language. He thought that the fact that the mother tongue isn't supposed to be compared is the most distinctive aspect of EA. "What the learner knows and does not know" and "end up enabling the teacher to supply him not only with the information that his hypothesis is wrong, but also, importantly, with the right sort of information or data for him to form a more adequate concept of a rule in the target language" are in fact the goals of error analysis (Corder, 1974, p. 170). The primary objective of this research is to investigate the kinds of mistakes that a group of Algerian university-level EFL students make in their written and oral expressions.

METHODS

Applied semantics is the endeavor to put the bits of knowledge coming about because of linguistic research to down to earth utilizes. First- and second-language instruction (such as: translation, lexicography, and so on). The field of language teaching, which focuses on the learner and the language learning process, is our area of linguistic application focus. How is this language learned, the subject of the linguist's study? To learn a language, we must investigate mental processes that take place in human minds. In this regard, Krashen (1987) discussed two phenomena that stood out: first language securing and second language learning. First language securing: Subconscious learning that is unaffected by explicit instruction about the L2 system or errors that violate the L2 rule system is referred to as acquisition. It takes place outside in nature. Language data is not organized as in a classroom setting. The infant has unlimited access to information. The child is simultaneously acquiring numerous skills. As a result, learning a first language is a mental and psychological process that happens naturally, without conscious thought. Learning a second

language: On the other hand, learning refers to a conscious process that occurs as a result of explicit instruction regarding L2 rule system errors. Later in life, one learns a second language. The individual already uses a language system to communicate. He or she already exhibits verbal behavior. In this instance, learning is conscious. The information is organized by prospectus architects. In contrast to the infant, the learner is not exposed to unlimited data. It occurs during formal instruction. The student isn't really youthful. To put it another way, a child's biological abilities make it possible for him or her to learn language for the first time. Noam Chomsky referred to this as LAD. i.e., a tool for learning a new language. The latter is a result of the environment in which children are born—Arabic in an Arabic environment—and is a predisposition to language acquisition. English in an English setting, for example). There was a predominate view of language that saw learners' errors as something to be avoided prior to the 1960s, when the behavioristic perspective dominated. Errors were viewed as a sign of mislearning and as detrimental to proper language learning processes. The behaviorist point of view maintains that inadequate teaching methods are to blame for mistakes that, if "perfect," would never be made. This way of thinking was thought to be naive because there is no such thing as a "perfect" methodology, especially since Chomsky came up with the Universal Grammar idea in 1965. The latter asserted that every individual possesses an inherent capacity that can direct him through a vast array of sentence generation options. Language teachers have begun to adopt the cognitive approach since then. Researchers' interest in learners' errors as a source of hypotheses formation is bolstered by Chomsky's theory. Corder was the first to advocate for the significance of mistakes in language learning (1967). He demonstrated that L2 learners' strategies could be inferred from their errors, which could be useful for researchers studying the L2 learning process. Selinker (1992) emphasized Corder's study's two major contributions to L2 learning. The first is that the learner's mistakes are organized, and the second is that they are not "negative" or "interfering," but rather a positive factor that shows that the hypothesis is being tested. The term "error" is the subject of numerous definitions. An error is defined as "a linguistic form or combination of forms which, in the same context, under the same conditions of production, would, in all likelihood, not be produced by the speakers' native speaker counterparts," as stated by Lennon (cited in Brown, 2000). In contrast, Corder (1967) distinguishes between the mistake that refers to idiosyncrasies in the learner's interlanguage that manifest the learner's system of operation while learning and the mistake that is a performance error due to a random guess or slip. The latter is referred to as L2, and it reflects the learner's interlanguage proficiency by deviating from the adult grammar of a native speaker. Mistakes are efficient and may give important

understanding into language securing in light of the fact that they are goofs in the student's hidden ability. At the point when local speakers commit errors, they can recognize and address them promptly in light of the fact that they have practically full information on the etymological design of their native language L2 learners, who are not native speakers, not only make mistakes but also commit errors. Because they only have a limited understanding of the target language, they are not always able to correct the mistakes they make. As a result, the mistakes made by the students reveal a lack of fundamental proficiency in the language they are learning.

RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

Errors are not responsible for the learning process, but they are why students make mistakes and why it is so hard for them to fix them. Language transfer is recognized as one of the main causes of errors by researchers who study second language acquisition (Corder, 1974; Scovel, 2001). However, we are able to identify the following additional error sources:

1. Interlingual interference or language transfer Errors of this kind are brought about by mother tongue interference.

Eg1. I followed him yesterday leisurely in the road. (Arabic thought: negative translation from Arabic to English) Examples: The police provided me with confidential information. Negative translation into English from French) Interference between languages: These kinds of mistakes happen when people are learning a second language, when they haven't really mastered the material. Errors can also be brought on by the difficulty or issue with language itself. According to Richards (1971), the following categories also apply to intralingual errors:

a) *Over-generalisation:*

E.g: He can swims. Instead of saying : He can swim or He swims.

b) *Simplification:* (Redundancy/ reduction)

E.g. I studied English for two *year*. (Instead of *years*)

c) *Communication base:*

E.g: Using "airball" instead of balloon (coinage)

d) *Induced errors:* Due to the teacher's presentation of the material:

E.g: as if= like. The learner will write the following sentence:

E.g: She cries *as if* the baby cries instead of writing: She cries *like* a baby.

d) *Analogical errors:* (started, goed)

E.g: He *goed* to school on foot.(Instead of saying went)

e) Ignorance of rule restrictions: the learner applies rules to context where they are not applicable (e.g. He made

me to go rest" through extension of the pattern "He asked/wanted me to go").

f) Incomplete application of rules: the learner fails to use a fully developed structure (e.g. "You like to sing?" in place of "Do you like to sing?")

g) False hypothesis: the learners do not fully understand a distinction in the target language (e.g. the use of "was" as a marker of past tense in "One day I was travelled.").

Errors are seen as a deliberate deviation by students who are still learning the L2 rules. Because they are reflective of the learner's current stage of L2 development, errors cannot be self-corrected.

In contrast, a mistake is defined as a random confirmation slip brought on by tiredness, excitement, or other factors, and the learner is able to easily self-correct. One of the most influential theories of second language acquisition is error analysis. It focuses on the comparison of L2 learners' acquired norms with the norms of the target language and the explanation of the errors found in the comparison. Error analysis, according to Crystal (1999, p. 108), is the study of the unacceptable forms produced by someone learning a language, particularly a foreign language. EA is defined as "the study of linguistic ignorance, the investigation of what people do not know and how they attempt to cope with their ignorance," according to James (1998).

Brown offers yet another definition of error analysis. "The process to observe, analyze, and classify the deviations from the rules of the second languages and then to reveal the systems operated by learner," was how he defined error analysis. Error analysis is defined as "a type of linguistic analysis that focuses on errors committed by learners," as stated by AbiSamara (2003). Errors, according to Corder (1967), are useful sources of information for three parties: for instructors, it pieces of information them on the advancement of the understudies; It provides evidence of how language is acquired or learned for researchers; It provides learners with resources to help them learn.

According to Brown (2000, p. 224), there are two primary types of errors: interlingual errors and intralingual errors. Errors that can be attributed to interference in a first language are referred to as interlingual (interference) errors. Negative interlingual transfer is to blame for these errors. Selinker was the first person to use the term "interlingua" (1972). According to AbiSamra (2003), p. 5, he used this term to describe systematic knowledge of an L2 that is independent of the learner's L1 and the target language. As indicated by Kavaliauskiene

(2009, p. 4), move of mistakes might happen in light of the fact that the students come up short on vital data in the second

language or the attentional ability to initiate the fitting second language schedule.

The two types of transfer are: both good and bad. The transfer may be called "positive transfer" or "facilitation" if the structure of the two languages is similar; in this case, the transfer is justified; or it may be called "negative transfer" or "interference" if the structure of the two languages is different.

According to Keshavarz (2003, p. 62), intralingual errors are not the result of language transfer but rather of inadequate or incomplete learning of the target language. According to Richards (1972), there are four primary types of intralingual errors: 1) Overgeneralization; 2) Ignorance of restrictions imposed by rules; 3) Incomplete application of rules; and 4) Hypothesis of false concepts. Later, he identifies six error-causing factors: 1) interference, 2) overgeneralization, 3) errors in performance, 4) indicators of transitional competence, 5) communication and assimilation strategies, and 6) mistakes made by teachers.

According to Stenson (1974), there are three primary causes of errors: (1) inadequate acquisition of the target grammar, (2) demands of the learning/teaching environment, and (3) errors caused by typical language performance issues.

One of the most unavoidable things in the world is making mistakes. During the process of learning a language, students benefit from making mistakes by receiving feedback that encourages them to try again and eventually achieve their desired goals. According to Vahdatinejad (2008), error analyses can be used to figure out what a student still needs to be taught. It reveals the deficiencies in the learner's competence that need to be addressed. Additionally, he distinguishes between lapses and errors (simple mistakes). As per him, slips

are created even by local speakers, and can be rectified without help from anyone else. Instead of requiring remediation for errors, they call for immediate correction. According to Mitchell and Myles (cited in Keshavarz, 2003), errors could reveal a developing system of the student's L2 language that is dynamic and open to changes and parameter resets if studied.

CONCLUSION

The primary errors that a group of Algerian university-level EFL students made in their written and spoken work have been documented in this study. It is possible to draw the conclusion, based on the discussion of the findings and the examples provided, that the Arabic speakers in this study committed a significant number of errors as a result of L1 transfer.

Language teachers should carefully assess the transfer and interference of the students' mother tongue in their spoken or written production in light of the obvious Arabic influences on their writing and speaking of English. Therefore, collecting these errors and asking students to evaluate them and determine whether or not they would

be able to correct them is one strategy for bringing attention to the impact that students' mother tongues have on their ability to learn English.

Some errors must be fixed; If not, they will turn into fossils. Teachers of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) should be familiar with Error Analysis and its related theories. Additionally, as language teachers, we should consider the teaching objectives, students' linguistic competence, their affective factors, and the efficiency of error correction when emphasizing error correction in the classroom. As a result, we are able to employ more adaptable error correction strategies and contribute more to the teaching and learning of English as a foreign language in the classroom. Error analysis is significant, but it also has some drawbacks. First, paying too much attention to mistakes made by students runs the risk of them forgetting to say the right thing in the second language, and teachers often become so preoccupied with catching mistakes in the classroom that they forget to correct them. While reducing errors is an important criterion for improving language proficiency, communicative fluency in a language is the ultimate objective of learning a second language. Overstressing production data is another flaw in error analysis. Comprehension of the facts in language is just as important as production. While comprehension data are just as important in gaining an understanding of the process of language acquisition as production data, production data often lends itself to analysis and becomes the prey of researchers. Thirdly, the avoidance strategy is not taken into account. It may be incorrect to assume that a student who avoids a particular sound, word, structure, or category of discourse does not struggle with it. Therefore, the absence of errors does not necessarily indicate native-like competence because students may be avoiding the very structure that causes them difficulty. Finally, error analysis can prevent us from seeing universal aspects of language rather than focusing too much on particular languages.

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